

Connect with GREI

All of the resources and information shared here and more can be accessed via the NIH Office of Data Science Strategy's GREI landing page:

bit.ly/ODSSGREI

Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative

A National Institutes of Health Office of Data Science Strategy Program

Share Your Feedback via the GREI GitHub Discussion Board

We invite the research community to share feedback with GREI via our GitHub discussion board:

bit.ly/GREIdiscuss

We would love to hear about how you are using GREI resources, suggestions for resource improvements, and ideas for new events and resources.

Data Sharing Resources for Researchers, Librarians, and Repository Managers

GREI is made possible by support from the NIH Office of Data Science Strategy/Office of the NIH Director through Other Transactions Agreement (OTA) Numbers OT2DB000001, OT2DB000002, OT2DB000003, OT2DB000004, OT2DB000005, OT2DB000006, and OT2DB000013.

About GREI

The Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative is an NIH Office of Data Science Strategy program which aims to develop collaborative approaches for data management and sharing through the inclusion of generalist repositories in the NIH data ecosystem, and to better enable sharing, discovery, and reuse of NIH-funded data in generalist repositories.

The GREI program employs a co-competition model in which seven established generalist repositories - Dataverse, Dryad, Figshare, Open Science Framework (OSF), Mendeley Data, Vivli, and Zenodo - are working together to fulfill both elements of the GREI mission:

To establish a common set of cohesive and consistent **capabilities, services, metrics, and social infrastructure** across generalist repositories

To raise general awareness and help researchers adopt **FAIR principles** to better share and reuse data

GREI Community Blog

Check out the GREI Community Blog for updates on our collaborative work.

medium.com/@blog-grei

GREI Resource Collection

Visit the GREI Community on Zenodo to find the resources highlighted at right and more, including a library of recordings and slides on a range of topics such as:

- *Best practices for data sharing in generalist repositories*
- *Best practices for finding data in generalist repositories*
- *Generalist repository use cases*
- *Data metrics in generalist repositories*

bit.ly/GREIZenodo

GREI Resource Highlights

Writing a Data Management & Sharing Plan

GREI's **Guide for Including a Generalist Repository in an NIH Data Management and Sharing (DMS) Plan** offers concise summaries, generalist repository-specific advice, and sample text for NIH DMS Plan sections 1-5 and an additional section on data sharing costs, assisting researchers in creating NIH-compliant plans when using a generalist repository.

doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14278957

Comparing & Selecting a Generalist Repository

The **Generalist Repository Comparison Chart** compares the seven GREI repositories across the NIH's desirable characteristics for data repositories. The companion **Generalist Repository Selection Flowchart** offers a decision tree to help users choose the best GREI repository for their data sharing needs.

doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3946719
doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11105429

Submitting Data for Publication and Sharing

GREI's **Best Practices for Data Submission in Generalist Repositories: A Checklist** offers comprehensive data management and curation guidance for the full research workflow to ensure data submitted to generalist repositories is of high-quality and aligned with FAIR principles. It also includes appendices on README files and metadata preparation.

doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14278906